

1. Brute Force SSH Single User attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ hydra -l admin -P pass.txt ssh://192.168.0.12
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service
organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-08-28 22:51:38
[WARNING] Many SSH configurations limit the number of parallel tasks, it is recommended to reduce the ta
sks: use -t 4
[WARNING] Restorefile (you have 10 seconds to abort... (use option -I to skip waiting)) from a previous
session found, to prevent overwriting, ./hydra.restore
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 25 login tries (l:1/p:25), ~2 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ssh://192.168.0.12:22/
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
675	Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
676	Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
677	Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
678	Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
679	Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
680	Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
> Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:51:50.325 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ssh data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 27 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_
failure id: 1756435910.131656 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:51:50.325 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.
29

> Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:51:50.320 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user ad
min from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ssh data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 3 rule.mail: false rule.level: 8 rule.description: Multiple login failure atte
mpt detected from 192.168.0.14 via ssh for user admin rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100030 rule.frequency: 5 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_failure id: 1756435910.131025
full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:51:50.320 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Multiple login failure attempt detected from 192.168.0.14 via ssh for user admin			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:07 Aug/29/2025 10:51:50
Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 10:51:50	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Brute Force Telnet Single User attack from Kali Linux

```
—(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ hydra -l admin -P pass.txt telnet://192.168.0.12
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service
organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-08-28 22:56:24
[WARNING] telnet is by its nature unreliable to analyze, if possible better choose FTP, SSH, etc. if available
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 25 login tries (1:1/p:25), ~2 tries per task
[DATA] attacking telnet://192.168.0.12:23/
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
723	Aug/29/2025 10:56:25	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
724	Aug/29/2025 10:56:25	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
729	Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
731	Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
725	Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
726	Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
727	Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user dmin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:56:26.796 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: telnet data.username: dmin rule.firedtimes: 55 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user dmin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_failure
id: 1756436186.145853 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user dmin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:56:26.796 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29
```

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:56:26.591 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user
admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telne
t manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: telnet data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 5 rule.mail: false rule.level: 8 rule.description: Multiple login failure
attempt detected from 192.168.0.14 via telnet for user admin rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100030 rule.frequency: 5 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_failure id: 175643618
6.145201 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via telnet timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:56:26.591 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Multiple login failure attempt detected from 192.168.0.14 via telnet for user admin			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:38 Aug/29/2025 10:56:26
Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 10:56:26	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Brute Force FTP Single User attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ hydra -l admin -P pass.txt ftp://192.168.0.12
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service
organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-08-28 22:58:51
[WARNING] Restorefile (you have 10 seconds to abort... (use option -I to skip waiting)) from a previous
session found, to prevent overwriting, ./hydra.restore
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 25 login tries (1:1/p:25), ~2 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ftp://192.168.0.12:21/
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
733	Aug/29/2025 10:59:03	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
734	Aug/29/2025 10:59:03	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
735	Aug/29/2025 10:59:03	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
736	Aug/29/2025 10:59:04	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
737	Aug/29/2025 10:59:04	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
738	Aug/29/2025 10:59:04	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:59:04.533 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ftp data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 60 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_
failure id: 1756436344.149485 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:59:04.533 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.
29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:59:04.499 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user ad
min from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ftp data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 6 rule.mail: false rule.level: 8 rule.description: Multiple login failure atte
mpt detected from 192.168.0.14 via ftp for user admin rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100030 rule.frequency: 5 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_failure id: 1756436344.148854
full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:59:04.499 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Multiple login failure attempt detected from 192.168.0.14 via ftp for user admin			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:13 Aug/29/2025 10:59:04
Aug/29/2025 10:59:04	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 10:59:04	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Brute Force SSH Multi User attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ hydra -L users.txt -P pass.txt -u -t 16 -f ssh://192.168.0.12
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service
organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-08-28 22:54:31
[WARNING] Many SSH configurations limit the number of parallel tasks, it is recommended to reduce the ta
sks: use -t 4
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 150 login tries (1:6/p:25), ~10 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ssh://192.168.0.12:22/
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
707	Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
709	Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
698	Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
702	Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
706	Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
700	Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user telecom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:54:34.536 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ssh data.username: telcom rule.firedtimes: 43 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login
_failure id: 1756436074.139341 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:54:34.536 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.0
8.29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 10:54:34.531 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user te
lcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ssh
system,error,critical login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login fail
ure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ssh system,error,critical login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via
ssh manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ssh data.username: telecom rule.firedtimes: 2 rule.mail: false rule.level: 11 rule.description: Brute force attack d
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via ssh for user telecom			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:12 Aug/29/2025 10:54:34
Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 10:54:34	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Wazuh Alert

Attacker : 192.168.0.14

Target : 192.168.0.12

Severity : Level 11

Time: 29-08-2025 ~ 10:54:34 WITA

Log :

Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via ssh for user telecom

10:54

1. Brute Force Telnet Multi User attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ hydra -L users.txt -P pass.txt -u -t 16 -f ssh://192.168.0.12
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service
organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-08-28 22:54:31
[WARNING] Many SSH configurations limit the number of parallel tasks, it is recommended to reduce the ta
sks: use -t 4
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 150 login tries (1:6/p:25), ~10 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ssh://192.168.0.12:22/
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
764	Aug/29/2025 11:02:52	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user dministrator from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
763	Aug/29/2025 11:02:52	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
762	Aug/29/2025 11:02:52	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
769	Aug/29/2025 11:02:53	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
770	Aug/29/2025 11:02:53	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet
768	Aug/29/2025 11:02:53	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via telnet

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:02:53.313 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh rule.firedtimes: 2 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.pci_dss: 10.2.4, 10.2.5 rule.hipaa: 164.312.b rule.tsc: CC6.1, CC6.8, CC7.2, CC7.3 rule.description: syslog: User authentication failure. rule.groups: syslog, access_control, authentication_failed rule.id: 2501 rule.nist_800_53: AU.14, AC.7 rule.gpg13: 7.8 rule.gdpr: IV_35.7.d, IV_32.2 location: 192.168.0.12 id: 1756436573.161373 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:02:53.313 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:02:53.231 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: system,error,critical login failure for user user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user admin123 from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user dministrator from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user user from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user dministrator from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via telnet system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via telnet manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: telnet data.username: root rule.firedtimes: 2 rule.mail: false
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via telnet for user root			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:17 Aug/29/2025 11:02:53
Aug/29/2025 11:02:53	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 11:02:53	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Wazuh Alert

Attacker : 192.168.0.14
Target : 192.168.0.12
Severity : Level 11
Time: 29-08-2025 ~ 11:02:53 WITA
Log :
Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via telnet for user root

1. Brute Force FTP Multi User attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)~[~]
└─$ hydra -L users.txt -P pass.txt -u -t 16 -f ftp://192.168.0.12
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service
organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-08-28 23:00:25
[WARNING] Restorefile (you have 10 seconds to abort... (use option -I to skip waiting)) from a previous
session found, to prevent overwriting, ./hydra.restore
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 150 login tries (1:6/p:25), ~10 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ftp://192.168.0.12:21/
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
747	Aug/29/2025 11:00:37	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user user from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
751	Aug/29/2025 11:00:38	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
753	Aug/29/2025 11:00:38	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
752	Aug/29/2025 11:00:38	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via ftp
755	Aug/29/2025 11:00:38	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ftp

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:00:38.438 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ftp data.username: administrator rule.firedtimes: 10 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ftp rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: use
r_login_failure id: 1756436438.155312 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ftp timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:00:38.438 _index: wazuh-ale
rts-4.x-2025.08.29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:00:38.427 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user us
er from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user telecom from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user telcom from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,
error,critical login failure for user user from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for
user admin from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via ftp system,error,critical login failure for user user from 192.168.0.14 via
ftp manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: ftp data.username: root rule.firedtimes: 1 rule.mail: false rule.level: 11 rule.description: Brute force attack dete
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via ftp for user root			
D ● Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:25	Aug/29/2025 11:00:38
Aug/29/2025 11:00:38	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 11:00:38	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

🔴 Wazuh Alert 🔴

Attacker : [192.168.0.14](#)

Target : [192.168.0.12](#)

Severity : Level 11

Time: 29-08-2025 ~ 11:00:38 WITA

Log :

Brute force attack detected from [192.168.0.14](#) via ftp for user root

11:00

1. Brute Force API Single User attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)~/apibrute
$ python3.13 mikrotikapi-bf.py -t 192.168.0.12 -u admin -p pass.txt

[WARN] You are using Python 3.13.5, which is newer than supported (max: 3.12.x).
[INFO] Some modules (e.g., 'telnetlib') may be deprecated or removed in this version.
[SUGGESTION] It's recommended to install Python 3.12.x (no need to uninstall your current version).

[?] Do you want to continue anyway? [y/N]: y

MikrotikAPI-BF

Mikrotik RouterOS API Bruteforce Tool v"1.16"
André Henrique (X / LinkedIn: @mrhenrike)
Please report tips, suggests and problems to X or LinkedIn
https://github.com/mrhenrike/MikrotikAPI-BF

[INFO] [23:14:01] [*] Starting brute force attack...
[INFO] [23:14:01] [*] Total Attempts 16...
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
776	Aug/29/2025 11:14:01	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via api
777	Aug/29/2025 11:14:01	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api
778	Aug/29/2025 11:14:01	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api
779	Aug/29/2025 11:14:06	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via api
780	Aug/29/2025 11:14:06	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via api
781	Aug/29/2025 11:14:06	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api
782	Aug/29/2025 11:14:06	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:14:06.353 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: rest-api data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 28 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_1
ogin_failure id: 1756437246.166199 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:14:06.353 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.
x-2025.08.29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:14:06.352 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: rest-api data.username: admin rule.firedtimes: 27 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_1
ogin_failure id: 1756437246.165873 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:14:06.352 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.
x-2025.08.29
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Multiple login failure attempt detected from 192.168.0.14 via api for user admin			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:31 Aug/29/2025 11:14:06
Aug/29/2025 11:14:06	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 11:14:06	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Brute Force API Multi User attack from Kali Linux

```

(kali@kali)~/apibrute
└─$ python3.13 mikrotikapi-bf.py -t 192.168.0.12 -d list.txt --threads 15

[WARN] You are using Python 3.13.5, which is newer than supported (max: 3.12.x).
[INFO] Some modules (e.g., 'telnetlib') may be deprecated or removed in this version.
[SUGGESTION] It's recommended to install Python 3.12.x (no need to uninstall your current version).

[?] Do you want to continue anyway? [y/N]: y

      [M]IKROTIK [A]PI [B]F
    [M]IKROTIK [A]PI [B]RUTE FORCE
  [M]IKROTIK [A]PI [B]RUTE FORCE

Mikrotik RouterOS API Bruteforce Tool v"1.16"
André Henrique (X / LinkedIn: @mrhenrike)
Please report tips, suggests and problems to X or LinkedIn
https://github.com/mrhenrike/MikrotikAPI-BF

[INFO] [23:28:28] [*] Starting brute force attack...
[INFO] [23:28:28] [*] Total Attempts 16...
  
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
811	Aug/29/2025 11:28:29	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user administrator from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api
812	Aug/29/2025 11:28:29	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user user2 from 192.168.0.14 via api
813	Aug/29/2025 11:28:29	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user user2 from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api
814	Aug/29/2025 11:28:30	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via api
815	Aug/29/2025 11:28:30	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user root from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api
816	Aug/29/2025 11:28:30	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user user1 from 192.168.0.14 via api
817	Aug/29/2025 11:28:30	memory	system, error, critical	login failure for user user1 from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```

Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:28:30.326 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srctp: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: rest-api data.username: user1 rule.firedtimes: 51 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user user1 from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_failure id: 1756438110.178714 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user user1 from 192.168.0.14 via rest-api timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:28:30.326 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:28:30.306 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srctp: 192.168.0.14 data.access_method: api data.username: user1 rule.firedtimes: 50 rule.mail: false
rule.level: 5 rule.description: Mikrotik log: Login failure for user user1 from 192.168.0.14 via api rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100003 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: user_login_failure id: 1756438110.178403 full_log: system,error,critical login failure for user user1 from 192.168.0.14 via api timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:28:30.306 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29
  
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via api for user root			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:06 Aug/29/2025 11:28:30
Aug/29/2025 11:28:30	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 11:28:30	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

```

syslogbali
🚨 Wazuh Alert 🚨
Attacker : 192.168.0.14
Target : 192.168.0.12
Severity : Level 11
Time: 29-08-2025 ~ 11:28:30 WITA
Log :
Brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 via api for user root
  
```

1. Brute Force SNMP-Brute (NSE) attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ nmap -sU -p 161 192.168.0.12 --script snmp-brute --script-args snmp-brute.communitiesdb=pass.txt
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-08-28 23:31 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.0.12
Host is up (0.0058s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
161/udp   open  snmp
MAC Address: 0C:74:97:4A:00:00 (Unknown)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 4.03 seconds
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
836	Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: administrator -- permission denied
837	Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: administrator123 -- permission denied
830	Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: password -- permission denied
831	Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: telecom -- permission denied
832	Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: telecom123 -- permission denied
834	Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: telecomadmin -- permission denied

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:31:57.312	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.snmp_community: administrator123 rule.firedtimes: 11 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: MikroTik: SNMP authentication failure from 192.168.0.14 (community: 'administrator123'). rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100004 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: snmp-authfail id: 1756438317.185148 full_log: snmp packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: administrator123 -- permission denied timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:31:57.312 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29</code>
Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:31:57.261	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.snmp_community: administrator rule.firedtimes: 10 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: MikroTik: SNMP authentication failure from 192.168.0.14 (community: 'administrator'). rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100004 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: snmp-authfail id: 1756438317.184821 full_log: snmp packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: administrator -- permission denied timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:31:57.261 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: SNMP multiple auth failure detected from 192.168.0.14 (community: 'root123').			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:16 Aug/29/2025 11:31:57
Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 11:31:57	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Brute Force SNMP-Brute (NSE) Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ nmap -sU -p 161 192.168.0.12 --script snmp-brute --script-args snmp-brute.communitiesdb=pass.lst -T4

Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-08-28 23:34 EDT
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
879	Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: estrella -- permission denied
887	Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: iloveme -- permission denied
878	Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: miguel -- permission denied
882	Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: mylove -- permission denied
880	Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: patrick -- permission denied
883	Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	disk	snmp	packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: poohbear -- permission denied

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:34:51.251 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.snmp_community: mylove rule.firedtimes: 34 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5
rule.description: MikroTik: SNMP authentication failure from 192.168.0.14 (community: 'mylove'). rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100004 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: snmp-authfail
id: 1756438491.200034 full_log: snmp packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: mylove -- permission denied timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:34:51.251 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29

Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:34:51.195 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.snmp_community: angela rule.firedtimes: 33 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5
rule.description: MikroTik: SNMP authentication failure from 192.168.0.14 (community: 'angela'). rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100004 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: snmp-authfail
id: 1756438491.199728 full_log: snmp packet(v1) from: 192.168.0.14 community: angela -- permission denied timestamp: Aug 29, 2025 @ 11:34:51.195 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.29
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: SNMP brute force attack detected from 192.168.0.14 (community: 'miguel').			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:09:44 Aug/29/2025 11:34:51
Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/29/2025 11:34:51	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Wazuh Alert

Attacker : **192.168.0.14**

Target : **192.168.0.12**

Severity : Level 11

Time: 29-08-2025 ~ 11:34:51 WITA

Log :

SNMP brute force attack detected from **192.168.0.14** (community: 'miguel').

11:34

1. DDoS Syn Fast attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo hping3 -S -p 22 -c 15000 --fast 192.168.0.12
HPING 192.168.0.12 (eth0 192.168.0.12): S set, 40 headers + 0 data bytes
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 DF id=0 sport=22 flags=SA seq=0 win=64240 rtt=15.1 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 DF id=0 sport=22 flags=SA seq=1 win=64240 rtt=6.4 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 DF id=0 sport=22 flags=SA seq=2 win=64240 rtt=6.8 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 DF id=0 sport=22 flags=SA seq=3 win=64240 rtt=7.9 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 DF id=0 sport=22 flags=SA seq=4 win=64240 rtt=10.4 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 DF id=0 sport=22 flags=SA seq=5 win=64240 rtt=9.6 ms
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
385	Aug/28/2025 19:52:02	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid s
386	Aug/28/2025 19:52:02	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid s
387	Aug/28/2025 19:52:02	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid s
388	Aug/28/2025 19:52:02	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid s

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:52:03.355 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 22 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 1821 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 162 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SYN-FAST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 22. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100005 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_syn_fast id: 1756381923.31277892 full_log: firewall,info SYN-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:1821->192.168.0.12:22, len 40 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:52:03.355 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28

> Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:52:03.184 input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 22 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 1820 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 161 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SYN-FAST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 22. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100005 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_syn_fast id: 1756381923.31277461 full_log: firewall,info SYN-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:1820->192.168.0.12:22, len 40 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:52:03.184 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SYN-FAST attack detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 22.			
D	Wazuh_Bl... 192.168.0.14	00:12:46	Aug/28/2025 19:52:00
391	Aug/28/2025 19:52:04	memory	system, info, account
392	Aug/28/2025 19:52:04	memory	system, info, account

user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

🔴 Wazuh Alert 🔴
Attacker : [192.168.0.14](#)
Target : [192.168.0.12](#)
Severity : Level 12
Time: 28-08-2025 ~ 19:52:01 WITA
Log :
DoS SYN-FAST attack detected from source [192.168.0.14](#) to [192.168.0.12](#) port 22.

1. DDoS Syn Flood attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo hping3 -S -p 22 -d 120 --flood --rand-source 192.168.0.12
HPING 192.168.0.12 (eth0 192.168.0.12): S set, 40 headers + 120 data bytes
hping in flood mode, no replies will be shown
^C
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0
932	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0
1...	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0
1...	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0
1...	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0
1...	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45	memory	firewall, info	SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 10:49:45.204	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 231.68.80.78 data.dstport: 22 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 28069 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 475 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SYN-FLOOD detected from 231.68.80.78 to 192.168.0.12 port 22. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100006 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_syn_flood id: 1756867785.7164473 full_log: firewall,info SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 231.68.80.78:28069->192.168.0.12:22, len 160 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 10:49:45.204 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 10:49:45.091	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 236.134.98.213 data.dstport: 22 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 27648 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 474 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SYN-FLOOD detected from 236.134.98.213 to 192.168.0.12 port 22. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100006 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_syn_flood id: 1756867785.7154425 full_log: firewall,info SYN-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 236.134.98.213:27648->192.168.0.12:22, len 160 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 10:49:45.091 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SYN-FLOOD attack detected from source 233.177.121.191 to 192.168.0.12 port 22.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	233.177.121.191	00:14:16	Sep/03/2025 10:49:37
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SYN-FLOOD attack detected from source 228.210.134.189 to 192.168.0.12 port 22.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	228.210.134.189	00:14:21	Sep/03/2025 10:49:42
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SYN-FLOOD attack detected from source 231.15.239.175 to 192.168.0.12 port 22.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	231.15.239.175	00:14:23	Sep/03/2025 10:49:45
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SYN-FLOOD attack detected from source 224.47.160.88 to 192.168.0.12 port 22.			
Sep/03/2025 10:49:45 memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api	
Sep/03/2025 10:49:45 memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api	

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Wazuh Alert

Attacker : **231.68.133.210**

Target : **192.168.0.12**

Severity : Level 15

Time: 03-09-2025 ~ 10:49:42 WITA

Log :

DoS SYN-FLOOD attack detected from source **231.68.133.210** to **192.168.0.12** port 22.

10:49

1. DDoS ICMP Fast attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo hping3 --icmp -c 15000 --fast 192.168.0.12
HPING 192.168.0.12 (eth0 192.168.0.12): icmp mode set, 28 headers + 0 data bytes
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 id=37516 icmp_seq=0 rtt=14.6 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 id=37521 icmp_seq=1 rtt=5.6 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 id=37530 icmp_seq=2 rtt=7.7 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 id=37536 icmp_seq=3 rtt=9.9 ms
len=46 ip=192.168.0.12 ttl=64 id=37544 icmp_seq=4 rtt=10.8 ms
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Aug/28/2025 19:59:47	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Aug/28/2025 19:59:47	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Aug/28/2025 19:59:47	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Aug/28/2025 19:59:47	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:59:47.754	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.icmp_type: 8 data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.icmp_code: 0 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 31 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS ICMP-FAST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100007 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_icmp_fast id: 1756382387.34527858 full_log: firewall,info ICMP-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto ICMP (type 8, code 0), 19 2.168.0.14->192.168.0.12, len 28 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:59:47.754 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28</code>
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:59:47.644	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.icmp_type: 8 data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.icmp_code: 0 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 30 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS ICMP-FAST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100007 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_icmp_fast id: 1756382387.34526826 full_log: firewall,info ICMP-FAST prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto ICMP (type 8, code 0), 19 2.168.0.14->192.168.0.12, len 28 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 19:59:47.644 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS ICMP-FAST attack detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:40 Aug/28/2025 19:59:45

Aug/28/2025 19:59:47	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/28/2025 19:59:47	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Wazuh Alert
Attacker : [192.168.0.14](#)
Target : [192.168.0.12](#)
Severity : Level 10
Time: 28-08-2025 ~ 19:59:46 WITA
Log :
DoS ICMP-FAST attack detected from source [192.168.0.14](#) to [192.168.0.12](#).
19:59

1. DDoS ICMP Flood attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo hping3 --icmp --flood --rand-source -d 1500 192.168.0.12
HPING 192.168.0.12 (eth0 192.168.0.12): icmp mode set, 28 headers + 1500 data bytes
hping in flood mode, no replies will be shown
^C
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:05:44	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
909	Aug/28/2025 20:05:44	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
820	Aug/28/2025 20:05:44	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
876	Aug/28/2025 20:05:44	memory	firewall, info	ICMP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

```
Time                               _source
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:05:44.298      input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh rule.firedtimes: 342 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS ICMP-FLOOD detected from to .
rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100008 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_icmp_flood id: 1756382744.36142253 full_log: firewall,info ICMP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0),
connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto ICMP, 231.78.32.91->192.168.0.12, len 152 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:05:44.298 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:05:44.296      input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.icmp_type: 8 data.srcip: 231.78.32.91 data.icmp_code: 0 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 341
rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS ICMP-FLOOD detected from 231.78.32.91 to 192.168.0.12. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100008 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos
_icmp_flood id: 1756382744.36141833 full_log: firewall,info ICMP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto ICMP (type 8, code 0),
231.78.32.91->192.168.0.12, len 1396 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:05:44.296 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS ICMP-FLOOD attack detected from source 237.159.217.7 to 192.168.0.12.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	237.159.217.7	00:14:06	Aug/28/2025 20:05:17
::: Wazuh Block: DoS ICMP-FLOOD attack detected from source 232.32.38.106 to 192.168.0.12.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	232.32.38.106	00:14:33	Aug/28/2025 20:05:44
::: Wazuh Block: DoS ICMP-FLOOD attack detected from source 237.62.24.24 to 192.168.0.12.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	237.62.24.24	00:14:36	Aug/28/2025 20:05:48

Aug/28/2025 20:05:44	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/28/2025 20:05:44	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

```
🚨 Wazuh Alert 🚨
Attacker : 232.32.38.106
Target : 192.168.0.12
Severity : Level 14
Time: 28-08-2025 ~ 20:05:23 WITA
Log :
DoS ICMP-FLOOD attack detected from source 232.32.38.106 to
192.168.0.12.
20:05
```


1. DDoS UDP Flood attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo hping3 --udp -p 1-1024 --flood --rand-source 192.168.0.12
HPING 192.168.0.12 (eth0 192.168.0.12): udp mode set, 28 headers + 0 data bytes
hping in flood mode, no replies will be shown
^C
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:11:55	memory	firewall, info	UDP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP,
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:11:55	memory	firewall, info	UDP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP,
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:11:55	memory	firewall, info	UDP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP,
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:11:55	memory	firewall, info	UDP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP,

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:11:55.565	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 236.171.67.144 data.dstport: 1 data.srcport: 34262 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 909 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS UDP-FLOOD detected from 236.171.67.144 to 192.168.0.12 port 1. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100010 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_udp_flood id: 1756383115.36621387 full_log: firewall,info UDP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP, 6.171.67.144:34262->192.168.0.12:1, len 28 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:11:55.565 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28</code>
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:11:55.564	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.srcip: 230.139.129.112 data.dstport: 1 data.srcport: 34074 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 908 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS UDP-FLOOD detected from 230.139.129.112 to 192.168.0.12 port 1. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100010 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_udp_flood id: 1756383115.36621808 full_log: firewall,info UDP-FLOOD prerouting: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:invalid src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP, 230.139.129.112:34074->192.168.0.12:1, len 28 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:11:55.564 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS UDP-FLOOD attack detected from source 229.98.6.174 to 192.168.0.12 port 1.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	229.98.6.174	00:13:56	Aug/28/2025 20:11:43
::: Wazuh Block: DoS UDP-FLOOD attack detected from source 227.20.71.167 to 192.168.0.12 port 1.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	227.20.71.167	00:14:03	Aug/28/2025 20:11:51
::: Wazuh Block: DoS UDP-FLOOD attack detected from source 236.255.226.59 to 192.168.0.12 port 1.			
D ● Wazuh_Bl...	236.255.226.59	00:14:08	Aug/28/2025 20:11:55
Aug/28/2025 20:11:55	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/28/2025 20:11:55	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

🚨 Wazuh Alert 🚨

Attacker : [226.197.26.36](#)

Target : [192.168.0.12](#)

Severity : Level 15

Time : 28-08-2025 ~ 20:11:48 WITA

Log :

DoS UDP-FLOOD attack detected from source [226.197.26.36](#) to [192.168.0.12](#) port 1.

20:12

1. Slow HTTP POST Flood attack from Kali Linux

```
Thu Aug 28 08:38:32 2025:
slowhttptest version 1.9.0
- https://github.com/shekyan/slowhttptest -
test type: SLOW BODY
number of connections: 300
URL: http://192.168.0.12/
verb: POST
cookies:
Content-length header value: 8192
follow up data max size: 66
interval between follow up data: 110 seconds
connections per seconds: 100
probe connection timeout: 5 seconds
test duration: 240 seconds
using proxy: no proxy
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:38:27	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:38:27	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:38:27	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Aug/28/2025 20:38:27	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:38:27.927	input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK data.srcport: 38134 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 156 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-POST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100014 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_post id: 1756384707.36750757 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK), 192.168.0.14:38134->192.168.0.12:80, len 52 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:38:27.927 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:38:27.924	input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK data.srcport: 38134 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 155 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-POST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100014 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_post id: 1756384707.36750315 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK), 192.168.0.14:38134->192.168.0.12:80, len 52 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 20:38:27.924 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SLOWHTTP-POST attack detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:33 Aug/28/2025 20:38:27
Aug/28/2025 20:38:27	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/28/2025 20:38:27	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

```
syslogbali
* Wazuh Alert *
Attacker : 192.168.0.14
Target : 192.168.0.12
Severity : Level 12
Time: 28-08-2025 ~ 20:38:27 WITA
Log :
DoS SLOWHTTP-POST attack detected from source 192.168.0.14
to 192.168.0.12 port 80.
20:38
```

1. Slow HTTP POST Flood Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
Wed Sep 3 11:02:50 2025:
slowhttptest version 1.9.0
- https://github.com/shekyaan/slowhttptest -
Test type: SLOW BODY
number of connections: 1000
URL: http://192.168.0.12/
verb: POST
cookie:
Content-Length header value: 8192
Follow up data max size: 22
interval between follow up data: 110 seconds
connections per seconds: 500
probe connection timeout: 3 seconds
test duration: 240 seconds
using proxy: no proxy
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
616	Sep/03/2025 11:02:55	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac
617	Sep/03/2025 11:02:55	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac
608	Sep/03/2025 11:02:55	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac
609	Sep/03/2025 11:02:55	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac
612	Sep/03/2025 11:02:55	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:02:54.716	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK,PSH data.srcport: 55544 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 489 rule.mail: true rule.level: 15 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100141 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_post_agg id: 1756868574.7681481 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac ac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK,PSH), 192.168.0.14:55544->192.168.0.12:80, len 387 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:02:54.716 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:02:54.704	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK,FIN data.srcport: 57608 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 487 rule.mail: true rule.level: 15 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100141 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_post_agg id: 1756868574.7680104 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac ac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK,FIN), 192.168.0.14:57608->192.168.0.12:80, len 52 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:02:54.704 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:02:46 Sep/03/2025 11:02:56
Sep/03/2025 11:02:56	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 11:02:56	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Wazuh Alert

Attacker : **192.168.0.14**

Target : **192.168.0.12**

Severity : Level 15

Time: 03-09-2025 ~ 11:02:54 WITA

Log :

DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-POST detected from **192.168.0.14** to **192.168.0.12** port 80.

11:16

1. Slow HTTP GET Flood attack from Kali Linux

```
Thu Aug 28 09:20:38 2025:
      slowhttptest version 1.9.0
- https://github.com/shekyan/slowhttptest -
test type:          SLOW HEADERS
number of connections: 300
URL:               http://192.168.0.12/
verb:              GET
cookie:
Content-Length header value: 4096
follow up data max size: 68
interval between follow up data: 10 seconds
connections per seconds: 100
probe connection timeout: 5 seconds
test duration:     240 seconds
using proxy:       no proxy
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
588	Aug/28/2025 21:20:40	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
591	Aug/28/2025 21:20:40	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
592	Aug/28/2025 21:20:40	memory	firewall, info	SLOWHTTP-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 21:23:00.413	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK data.srcport: 33698 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 212 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-GET detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100013 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_get id: 1756387380.38283986 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK), 192.168.0.14:33698->192.168.0.12:80, len 64 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 21:23:00.413 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28</code>
> Aug 28, 2025 @ 21:23:00.411	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK data.srcport: 33698 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 211 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-GET detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100013 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_get id: 1756387380.38283546 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK), 192.168.0.14:33698->192.168.0.12:80, len 64 timestamp: Aug 28, 2025 @ 21:23:00.411 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.08.28</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SLOWHTTP-GET attack detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80.			
D	Wazuh_Blocked_IPs	192.168.0.14	00:14:55 Aug/28/2025 21:20:40
Aug/28/2025 21:20:40	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Aug/28/2025 21:20:40	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

```
syslogbali
Wazuh Alert
Attacker : 192.168.0.14
Target : 192.168.0.12
Severity : Level 12
Time: 28-08-2025 ~ 21:20:39 WITA
Log :
DoS SLOWHTTP-GET attack detected from source 192.168.0.14
to 192.168.0.12 port 80.
21:20
```

1. Slow HTTP GET Flood Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
Wed Sep 3 11:21:57 2025:
slowhttptest version 1.9.0
- https://github.com/shekyaan/slowhttptest -
test type: SLOW HEADERS
number of connections: 1000
URL: http://192.168.0.12/
verb: GET
cookie:
Content-Length header value: 4096
follow up data max size: 52
interval between follow up data: 10 seconds
connections per seconds: 500
probe connection timeout: 3 seconds
test duration: 240 seconds
using proxy: no proxy
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	firewall.info	SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac C

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:22:24.987	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK,PSH data.srcport: 33920 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 1,006 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100131 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_get_agg id: 1756869744.8858239 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK,PSH), 192.168.0.14:33920->192.168.0.12:80, len 83 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:22:24.987 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:22:24.986	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 80 data.flags: ACK,PSH data.srcport: 33920 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 1,005 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100131 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: dos_slowhttp_get_agg id: 1756869744.8857784 full_log: firewall,info SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:established src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (ACK,PSH), 192.168.0.14:33920->192.168.0.12:80, len 83 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:22:24.986 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET attack detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 80.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:31 Sep/03/2025 11:22:24
Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 11:22:24	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

5. Active Response sends Telegram Notifications

Attacker : [192.168.0.14](#)
Target : [192.168.0.12](#)
Severity : Level 15
Time: 03-09-2025 ~ 11:22:14 WITA
Log :
DoS SLOWHTTP-AGG-GET attack detected from source [192.168.0.14](#) to [192.168.0.12](#) port 80. 11:23

1. Port Scanning TCP Connect Scan attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ nmap -sT 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 11:51 WITA
Nmap scan report for 192.168.0.12
Host is up (0.014s latency).
Not shown: 994 closed tcp ports (conn-refused)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
21/tcp    open  ftp
22/tcp    open  ssh
23/tcp    open  telnet
80/tcp    open  http
2000/tcp  open  cisco-scp
8291/tcp  filtered unknown
MAC Address: 0C:74:97:4A:00:00 (Unknown)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 12.86 seconds
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:51:54	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:51:54.879	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 35500 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 47304 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 3,089 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 35500. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100015 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp id: 1756871514.10981582 full_log: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:47304->192.168.0.12:35500, len 60 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:51:54.879 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:51:54.876	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 5679 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 44802 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 3,088 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 5679. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100015 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp id: 1756871514.10981147 full_log: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:44802->192.168.0.12:5679, len 60 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:51:54.876 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

1. Port Scanning TCP Connect Scan Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ nmap -sT -T4 -p- 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 11:57 WITA
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: TCP Port Scanning Aggressive detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 32725.			
D	● Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:25 Sep/03/2025 11:57:27
Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,
1...	Sep/03/2025 11:57:27	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00,

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:57:27.677	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 61367 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 50608 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 270 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 61367. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 10001</code> <code>6 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756871847.20447917 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:50608->192.168.0.12:61367, len 60 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:57:27.677 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:57:27.676	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 61367 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 50608 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 269 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 61367. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 10001</code> <code>6 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756871847.20447475 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:50608->192.168.0.12:61367, len 60 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 11:57:27.676 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

1. Port Scanning Stealth Scan attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ nmap -sS 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 12:01 WITA
Nmap scan report for 192.168.0.12
Host is up (0.041s latency).
Not shown: 994 closed tcp ports (reset)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
21/tcp    open  ftp
22/tcp    open  ssh
23/tcp    open  telnet
80/tcp    open  http
2000/tcp  open  cisco-scp
8291/tcp  open  unknown
MAC Address: 0C:74:97:4A:00:00 (Unknown)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 17.21 seconds
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:01:35	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN),

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:01:35.498	<code>input.type: log</code> <code>agent.name: wazuh</code> <code>agent.id: 000</code> <code>manager.name: wazuh</code> <code>data.protocol: TCP</code> <code>data.srccip: 192.168.0.14</code> <code>data.dstport: 211</code> <code>data.flags: SYN</code> <code>data.srccport: 59186</code> <code>data.dstip: 192.168.0.12</code> <code>rule.firedtimes: 1,219</code> <code>rule.mail: false</code> <code>rule.level: 5</code> <code>rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 211.</code> <code>rule.groups: mikrotik</code> <code>rule.id: 100015</code> <code>location: 192.168.0.12</code> <code>decoder.name: port_scan_tcp</code> <code>id: 1756872095.21292418</code> <code>full_log: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:59186->192.168.0.12:211, len 44</code> <code>timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:01:35.498</code> <code>_index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:01:35.497	<code>input.type: log</code> <code>agent.name: wazuh</code> <code>agent.id: 000</code> <code>manager.name: wazuh</code> <code>data.protocol: TCP</code> <code>data.srccip: 192.168.0.14</code> <code>data.dstport: 211</code> <code>data.flags: SYN</code> <code>data.srccport: 59186</code> <code>data.dstip: 192.168.0.12</code> <code>rule.firedtimes: 1,218</code> <code>rule.mail: false</code> <code>rule.level: 5</code> <code>rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 211.</code> <code>rule.groups: mikrotik</code> <code>rule.id: 100015</code> <code>location: 192.168.0.12</code> <code>decoder.name: port_scan_tcp</code> <code>id: 1756872095.21291986</code> <code>full_log: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:59186->192.168.0.12:211, len 44</code> <code>timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:01:35.497</code> <code>_index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

1. Port Scanning Stealth Scan Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ nmap -sS -T4 -p- 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 12:23 WITA
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: TCP Port Scanning Aggressive detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 54061.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:30 Sep/03/2025 12:23:52
Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:23:52	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN).

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:23:52.103	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 40407 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 54189 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 286 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 40407. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 10001 6 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756873432.56933374 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54189->192.168.0.12:40407, len 44 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:23:52.103 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:23:52.102	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 48015 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 54189 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 283 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 48015. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 10001 6 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756873432.56931172 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54189->192.168.0.12:48015, len 44 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:23:52.102 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>

1. Port Scanning UDP Scan attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ nmap -sU --top-ports 100 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 12:27 WITA
Nmap scan report for 192.168.0.12
Host is up (0.0057s latency).
Not shown: 97 closed udp ports (port-unreach)
PORT      STATE      SERVICE
68/udp    open|filtered dhcpc
123/udp   open              ntp
161/udp   open              snmp
MAC Address: 0C:74:97:4A:00:00 (Unknown)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 10.48 seconds
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:27:19	memory	firewall, info	UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:27:19	memory	firewall, info	UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:27:19	memory	firewall, info	UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:27:19	memory	firewall, info	UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:27:19	memory	firewall, info	UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:27:19	memory	firewall, info	UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:27:12.371	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: UDP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 626 data.srcport: 34829 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 74 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: UDP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 626. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100017 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_udp id: 1756873632.57077536 full_log: firewall,info UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP, 192.168.0.14:34829->192.168.0.12:626, len 58 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:27:12.371 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:27:12.370	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: UDP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 626 data.srcport: 34829 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 73 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: UDP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 626. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100017 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_udp id: 1756873632.57077121 full_log: firewall,info UDP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP, 192.168.0.14:34829->192.168.0.12:626, len 58 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:27:12.370 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>

1. Port Scanning UDP Scan Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)~$ nmap -sU -sV -T4 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 12:28 WITA
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	firewall, info	UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:28:52.491	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: UDP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 20262 data.srcport: 41503 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 43 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: UDP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 20262. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100018 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_udp_agg id: 1756873732.57361041 full_log: firewall,info UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP, 192.168.0.14:41503->192.168.0.12:20262, len 28 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:28:52.491 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:28:52.489	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: UDP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 20262 data.srcport: 41503 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 42 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: UDP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 20262. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100018 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_udp_agg id: 1756873732.57360616 full_log: firewall,info UDP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto UDP, 192.168.0.14:41503->192.168.0.12:20262, len 28 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:28:52.489 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: UDP Port Scanning Aggressive detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 24854.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:27 Sep/03/2025 12:28:52

Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 12:28:52	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Port Scanning No Ping Scan attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)~$ nmap -Pn 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 12:31 WITA
Nmap scan report for 192.168.0.12
Host is up (0.015s latency).
Not shown: 994 closed tcp ports (reset)
PORT      STATE SERVICE
21/tcp    open  ftp
22/tcp    open  ssh
23/tcp    open  telnet
80/tcp    open  http
2000/tcp  open  cisco-scp
8291/tcp  open  unknown
MAC Address: 0C:74:97:4A:00:00 (Unknown)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 3.28 seconds
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

Log					
#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message	
778	Sep/03/2025 12:31:22	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	
773	Sep/03/2025 12:31:22	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	
774	Sep/03/2025 12:31:22	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:31:23	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:31:23	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:31:23	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:31:23	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto	

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:31:23.094	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:46600->192.168.0.12:4550, len 44 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:46600->192.168.0.12:2179, len 44 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:46600->192.168.0.12:2179, len 44 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:46600->192.168.0.12:1122, len 44 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:46600->192.168.0.12:9415, len 44 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), co</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:31:23.093	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 2179 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 46600 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 56,469 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 2179. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 1000 15 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp id: 1756873883.58248722 full_log: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:46600->192.168.0.12:2179, len 44 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:31:23.093 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

1. Port Scanning No Ping Scan Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ nmap -Pn -T4 192.168.0.12
Starting Nmap 7.95 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-09-03 12:32 WITA
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
675	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
663	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto
664	Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:32:53.619	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 8443 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 45579 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 345 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 8443. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100016 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756873973.58703655 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:45579->192.168.0.12:8443, len 44 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:32:53.619 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:32:53.619	<pre>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 8443 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 45579 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 344 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 8443. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100016 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756873973.58703216 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 0c:2c:4a:11:00:00, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:45579->192.168.0.12:8443, len 44 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:32:53.619 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</pre>

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: TCP Port Scanning Aggressive detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 7741.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:27 Sep/03/2025 12:32:53
Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 12:32:53	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged out from 192.168.0.5 via api

1. Port Scanning Masscan attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo masscan 192.168.0.12 -p1-1024 --rate 500
Starting masscan 1.3.2 (http://bit.ly/14GZzcT) at 2025-09-03 04:37:44 GMT
Initiating SYN Stealth Scan
Scanning 1 hosts [1024 ports/host]
Discovered open port 23/tcp on 192.168.0.12
Discovered open port 21/tcp on 192.168.0.12
Discovered open port 22/tcp on 192.168.0.12
Discovered open port 80/tcp on 192.168.0.12
```

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:37:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:37:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:37:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:37:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:37:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto
1...	Sep/03/2025 12:37:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:37:15.965	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 previous_output: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54232->192.168.0.12:23903, len 40 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54232->192.168.0.12:27246, len 40 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54232->192.168.0.12:59383, len 40 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54232->192.168.0.12:54088, len 40 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54232->192.168.0.12:36642, len 40 firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown</code>
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:37:15.964	<code>input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 27246 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 54232 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 63,158 rule.mail: false rule.level: 5 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 27246. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100015 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp id: 1756874235.62902249 full_log: firewall,info TCP-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56:f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54232->192.168.0.12:27246, len 40 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:37:15.964 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03</code>

1. Port Scanning Masscan Aggressive attack from Kali Linux

```
(kali@ kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo masscan 192.168.0.12 -p1-65535 --rate 5000
Starting masscan 1.3.2 (http://bit.ly/14GZzcT) at 2025-09-03 04:39:30 GMT
Initiating SYN Stealth Scan
Scanning 1 hosts [65535 ports/host]
Discovered open port 8728/tcp on 192.168.0.12
Discovered open port 23/tcp on 192.168.0.12
Discovered open port 2000/tcp on 192.168.0.12
Discovered open port 8729/tcp on 192.168.0.12
^Cwaiting several seconds to exit...
```

4. Active Response blocks the Attacker's IP

List	Address	Timeout	Creation Time
::: Wazuh Block: TCP Port Scanning Aggressive detected from source 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 60025.			
D	Wazuh_Bl...	192.168.0.14	00:14:21 Sep/03/2025 12:39:48
Sep/03/2025 12:39:49	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api
Sep/03/2025 12:39:49	memory	system, info, account	user wazuh-user logged in from 192.168.0.5 via api

2. Mikrotik Displays Logs and Sends to Wazuh via Syslog

#	Time	Buffer	Topics	Message
485	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
659	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
660	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
655	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
656	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
759	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
760	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto
570	Sep/03/2025 12:39:48	memory	firewall, info	TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto

3. Wazuh Analyzes Logs and Executes Active Responses according to Severity Level

Time	_source
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:40:01.943	input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 48297 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 54369 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 5,092 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 48297. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100016 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756874401.82646263 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54369->192.168.0.12:48297, len 40 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:40:01.943 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03
Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:40:01.920	input.type: log agent.name: wazuh agent.id: 000 manager.name: wazuh data.protocol: TCP data.srcip: 192.168.0.14 data.dstport: 40386 data.flags: SYN data.srcport: 54369 data.dstip: 192.168.0.12 rule.firedtimes: 5,087 rule.mail: false rule.level: 6 rule.description: TCP Port Scanning detected from 192.168.0.14 to 192.168.0.12 port 40386. rule.groups: mikrotik rule.id: 100016 location: 192.168.0.12 decoder.name: port_scan_tcp_agg id: 1756874401.82555538 full_log: firewall,info TCP-AGG-SCAN input: in:ether1 out:(unknown 0), connection-state:new src-mac 00:50:56f6:69:1b, proto TCP (SYN), 192.168.0.14:54369->192.168.0.12:40386, len 40 timestamp: Sep 3, 2025 @ 12:40:01.920 _index: wazuh-alerts-4.x-2025.09.03